

THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL DIMENSION OF AL-BIRUNI'S MANUSCRIPT COPY "KITAB AL-TAFHIM LI AWA'IL SINA'AT AL-TANJIM -TO AL BIRUNI", IN SILK ROAD INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract. *The verification of the manuscript, the most significant type of manuscript, is a challenging task that requires careful archeological investigation. This paper examines The archaeological dimension of Al-Biruni's manuscript copy "Kitab al-Tafhim li Awa'il Sina'at al-Tanjim -to Al Biruni", in silk road international university, From an archaeological point of view, this manuscript is considered a movable antiquity. The aim of this research study :*

- 1- *What previous studies have been done on Al-Biruni's version, whether the original or what was based on copies-*
- 2- *Introducing the author and his works and introducing the manuscript of the study itself*
- 3- *Trace the history of the manuscript since it was written*
- 4- *A comparison between this copy and other copies preserved in various places.*
- 5- *This research will demonstrate the importance of applying the archaeological methodology in studying this manuscript.*

Key words: *Manuscript, "Kitab Al- Tafhim Li Awa'il Sina at AL-Tanjim, Al-Biruni, archaeological.*

Introducing the author of the manuscript "Kitab Al- Tafhim Li Awa'il Sina at AL-Tanjim"

He is Abu al-Rayhan Muhammad bin Ahmed al-Biruni, born on the second of Dhu al-Hijjah 362AH, which is equivalent to September 4, 973AD. We find that his place of birth is different, as some went that he was born in a town called al-Birun, which was in Sindh. Some scholars went that he was born in Haifa,¹ " Uzbekistan ", and some went that he was born in Khwarizm , but recent studies have proven that he was born in Kath , which is now called "al-Biruni" and was the capital of the Khwarizmian empire. He lived a modest life away from poverty. When he was born in 973AD, the Persian civilization was in full bloom, and the eastern region of the Islamic Empire was strong politically , and it was interested in the transfer of culture and the development of literature and the arts , and he began his studies at an early age under the supervision of the famous astronomer and mathematician, Abu Nasr Mansour, "Emir of the Ruling Sons of Iraq" At the age of seventeen, he had already shown his readiness by calculating the presentation of city kath, and from his own observation he knew that the earth was round , and at the age of 22 he had a high skill in cartography² .

¹ Daud Abdul-Fattah Batchelor , Al-Bîrûnî: Outstanding 'Modern' Scientist of the Golden Age of Islamic Civilisation,

² Hakim Mohammed Said and Ansar Zahid Khan, *Al-Biruni: His Times, Life and Works* (Karachi: Hamdard Academy, 1981)p 18.

At the end of the tenth century and the beginning of the eleventh century, there was a period of great turmoil in the Islamic world, and there were civil wars in the region where al-Biruni lived, and Khwarizm was at that time part of the Samanid Empire that ruled from Bukhara.³

He fled Khwarizm and moved to city of "Al-Rey" and worked in a famous center for astronomy during that time, and with difficulties in city "AL-Rey" he stayed there for three years and then moved to Gorgan at the invitation of its ruler, Sultan "Shams al-Ma 'ali bin Qaboos" where he completed the famous book about "Antiquities" and dedicated it to the Sultan.

After ten years in Gorgan, he received an invitation from the new Mamoun ruler, Abu al-Hasan Ali, so al-Biruni left for Khwarizm, where interest in science and scientists flourished. After Al-Mamoun, Abu Al-Abbas took over, who paid attention to Al-Biruni.

When Mahmoud Al-Ghazanawi took over, he attacked "Kath" and annexed it to him in 1017AD, so Mahmoud asked "to bring Al-Biruni to him, and include him in his armies that conquered India, and Mahmoud took control of the northern parts of India, and Al-Biruni conducted and determined the latitudes of these cities and appeared adept in astronomy. After the death of Sultan Mahmoud in 1030AD, his oldest son Masoud took power and treated Peroni more gently until he died, and after the death of Sultan Mahmoud's son, Peroni continued his amazing scientific production until his death, and he died at the age of 78AD, leaving a tremendous amount of knowledge.

The most important his works :

This scientist did not stop researching and studying for one moment, and his serious scientific life resulted in more than one hundred and twenty books, some of which were translated into English, French, German and Latin, and Westerners took them and benefited from them.⁴ He produced more than 146 titles in many specializations, of which there are only 22 works. It covered astronomy (35), Astrolabe (4), astrology (23), chronology (5), time measurement (2), geography (9), cartography (10), mathematics, arithmetic, and trigonometry (15), mechanics (2), and medicine and pharmacy (2) and meteorology (1), gemstones (2), history (2), India (2), religion and philosophy (3), literary works (16), magic (2), and nine unclassified books.⁵

Definition of manuscript " Kitab Al Tafhīm Li Awail Sina at AL-Tanjīm"

It was written in the Persian language in the year 660 AH, and the numbered at the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies (3423), Uzbekistan, and the manuscript preserved at the Silk Roads International University was copied from the copy of the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies.⁶ (figure 1)

As for the reason for Al-Biruni's writing of this manuscript, it was written for a student from Iran called "Rayhana bint Al-Hussein" or Al-Hasan Al-Khwarizmi. It was written during the reign of Sultan Mahmoud Al-Ghaznawi in 420 AH, corresponding to 1341 AD. We find that the author explicitly mentioned the date in writing this book in the third chapter when described the world and the conditions of the heavens and the earth, When he talking about the calendar mentioned "Tuesday, which is the twenty-fifth of Ramadan, which is the day of four hundred and

³ Charles Coulston, the Book of instruction on the Elements, volume 111, new York, p 148.

⁴ Mohammad Noviani Ardi and others, Al-Biruni: A Muslim Critical Thinker, international journal of nusantara islam, vol,4, 2016, p3.

⁵ Arthur Upham Pope, "Al-Biruni as a thinker" in Al-Biruni Commemoration Volume (Calcutta: Iran Society, 1951), p. 281.

⁶ Abdul Rahman Farfour and Muhammad Mutee, Selected manuscripts from the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies in Tashkent, Al Majid Society Center for Culture and Heritage, 1995, p 101.

twenty Hijri years and the seventh of 1340 AD. This manuscript is divided into five chapters: the first semester in geometry, the second semester in arithmetic and algebra, the third semester in geography and knowledge of regions, the fourth semester in laboratory preservation, and the fifth semester in the rulings of astronomy (figure 1,2, 3)

The goal of this book is to simplify the principles of astronomy, in the form of 530 questions and answers, in a format that is easy for beginners to understand, and to make each new topic begin with a question for a student and end with an innovative answer from the professor. It deals with engineering issues, mathematical operations, astronomy, time series, and how to use the astrolabe and For astronomical research.

This manuscript was documented by UNESCO in the Memory of the World Program in 2011, as the oldest manuscript in the Persian language and included in the UNESCO List of Heritage⁷.

Formal features of this manuscript” “Kitab Al- Tafhim Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjim”

This copy is located in 486 pages that include in one volume, the length of the book is 26cm, its width is 20cm, written on old papers, and it shows traces of water on parts of which water may have fallen (figure 1). The first page includes the title of the copy, which is "“ Kitab Al-Tafhim Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjim". (figure4) We find that it used black ink in writing the title , and it used red ink in the word "astrology " or "AL-Tanjim. We note that the author used the word "book" or "kitab" at the beginning of the title, which indicates that he will address a specific problem or be in line with an important event or reality, and that he refersto the framework of author's freedom in addressing this mathematical approach, so he wrote about it an intellectual framework of his own. (figure4)

The context of the formal features of this copy, we find that writing of the word "astrology "or AL-Tanjim” came small and in red , and the transcriber wanted the title to be in an attractive visual focus for the reader, which indicates the skill of the transcriber on the one hand and his desire to achieve the visual dimension on the other hand.(figure4)

Then is followed by the supplication and the date of this copy in the month of Rajab in the year 839/ January 1436 and it was in red. We find here two dates for this copy, one written in the beginning of the text and the second in the third chapter inside the book , but it is likely that this Persian copy was written before the Arabic version, perhaps by Abu al-Rayhan, who was fluent in Arabic and Persian, or one of them was copied from the other, as the two copies came exactly identical, but what makes me see that the Persian version precedes the Arabic version in writing is that this book was written specifically for a Persian student, Rihanna bint Al-Hussein or Al-Hassan Al-Khwarizmi. Perhaps Abu al-Rayhan used the Persian language so that this student can easily understand and study the book. the Researcher see that the Persian version was written when Al-Biruni was 58 years old, but it was copied to Samarqand two hundred years later, based on the history of the Institute of Al-Birun, which is preserved in the copy , and supplication for this author consisting of five lines in the middle of the page.

This is followed by the name of the author , and it is noted that he mentioned the fourth name of the well-known author, which is "Al-Biruni", and it is possible to distinguish it from the rest of the name , and then comes the writing of the phrase "the mercy of God on him " , which indicates that this wording is not the wording of Al-Biruni himself , but is due to the fact that it

⁷ Muhammad Al-Bukhari, Arabic Manuscripts in the Republic of Uzbekistan, Al-Ma'rifa Magazine, No. 457, 2001, p 198.

was in the body of the page by the Copyist or the scribe of this copy of the transcriber and the date of this copy . To complete the formal features, we find that the number of lines of each page of the manuscript ranges between 13-15 lines , and it is noted that the ratio between the measurements and width of the page paper and its height is equal to the width and height of the area on which the text is written.(figure 4)

The original text was written in Persian in a black inked copy font, and it is noted that the font in which this copy was written is a good font indicating the level of the copier's skill in writing the font. It is also noted that the copier used red ink in writing some words, letters and marks separating the paragraphs The original text was written in Persian in a black inked copy font, and it is noted that the font in which this copy was written is a good font indicating the level of the copier's skill in writing the font. It is also noted that the copier used red ink in writing some words, letters and marks separating the paragraphs of the sentence, and this is one of the important formal features in the study of this copy.(figure4,5)

If we examine the sites where red ink is used, it becomes clear to us the following:

-Use on the first page in the manuscript, which includes the title of the book in the word " astrology " or "Tanjim" in order to highlight this word in the title so as to attract the eye of the reader.

- The use of red ink in some words inside the manuscript text, and the copyist wanted to highlight them within the framework of the author's formulation, which represents an important turn in the formulation or represents a name for a country or a name for a specific planet, such as the word engineering on the second page of the manuscript .

-used in writing the head of some letters, and in the letters "waw," in order to draw the reader's attention to the style of conjunction in the text. "Al-Kanani" indicated that this matter was one of the methodologies of transcription in the Middle Ages.

- One of the important formal features in the writing of the text is the use of black ink at the beginning of some words with a larger size, and he used to use some letters or lengthen some letters than usual in some words, especially when starting to ask in order to draw the reader's attention to these words .

-One of the formal features of this copy is the absence of diacritics in words.

- The Copyist also wrote some words in the margin or made some corrections to the copy as it represents in itself a formal dimension of the original copy.

Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library copy of the manuscript"Kitab Al- Tafhīm Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjīm" number dated (1238 AD).

When exposed to the formal features of this copy:

We find this copy it is located in(252) pages only , within one volume, deposit number: PPN746436718⁸,and the first page of the manuscript we find that it is full of phrases at the beginning of which the date of this copy written in Arabic "Shahr Safar, year ninety-seven" appears, followed by the title of the book and came a little different from the version of the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies and copy in "silk Road university "(figure 6).we can see the word "for the first industry" or Li Awail Sinaat " was canceled , The title in this copy is as follows "at-Tafhīm fī 'ilm at-tanġīm" and This word"Kitab " and "Li Awail Sinaat" may have been added to the title later as we found in the version of the Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies.The

⁸ <https://digital.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/werkansicht/?PPN=PPN746436718>

author may have amended the title by adding these words in subsequent copies of the manuscript.(figure6)

As a continuation of the formal features comes after that the name of the author "Abi al-Rayhan Muhammad bin Ahmed al-Biruni" and the title and the name of the author was written in black ink in Naskh script, followed by mentioning the names of God, and a Quranic verse⁹. Then we pray to the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him), and this Writing came in the middle of the page of six horizontal lines in black, and after that we find a small seal that is unclear about these words, but we can interpret some of them (طالع من الفقير الى الله البيروني سنة 97) (talae from Al-Faqbar to Allah Al-Biruni in the year 97) This seal indicates that the one who wrote this copy is "Abu Al-Rayhan." Al-Biruni himself, in the year 97, which date was found in the introduction to the manuscript and was referred to previously.

At the top of the page, we find another incomplete signature: "طالع الى المغفور على بن ناصر" "See in ... To the late ... 'Alī ibn Nāṣir al-Dīn ibn .. The rest of the writing was lost. This may be the name of the scribe who copied the manuscript after writing Al-Biruni, and making amendments to it.

One of the formal features of this copy is on the second page of the copy of the manuscript, starting with the basmala, and praying for the Prophet, and this feature is found in the copy preserved in the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies, and then followed by that second line (figure7). The title of the manuscript includes "the at-Tafhīm fī 'ilm at-taṅṅīm" and the name of the author, in which the copyist made mistakes and corrected the name twice by writing the name of Muhammad, which was inadvertently dropped by the copyist, and once by writing the name of Al-Biruni in the left margin, all of which are indications that confirm that whoever copied this copy is another person and not Al-Biruni and may have been copied after his death. Red durations were used in writing the name of the book and the author in order to draw the reader's attention to this paragraph and affect its visual vision.(figure 7)

- Complementing the formal features of the manuscript, we find that the text inside the manuscript consists of 19 lines, except for the first page, which consists of (17) lines, and we note the measurements between the width and paper of the page and its height. The copyist used it often to write on it, so that it was very close to the golden ratio of the book, and this is what we did not find in the manuscript preserved in the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies (preserved at the International Silk Road University)

-This copy was also written in black ink, and the red ink was used in some words, such as the Biruni copy at the Institute of Oriental Studies and which is preserved at the International Silk Road University.

-We note that the use of the names of God and the Quranic verse was not found in the previous version of Al-Biruni in institute of oriental studied, and here makes us ask an important question. Does this phrase represent an addition by the copyist as he will do a large work, which is to copy a large number of this copy, or that it is an original text in the original text of Al-Biruni, but I can not cut the answer, but the absence of these phrases in the same way in the previous version makes me say that the copyist added them, but it must be borne in mind that below this phrase we find the stamp of Al-Biruni, which makes me say that Al-Biruni wrote these phrases himself and that they were an original part with the corpus and lost with time. The second explanation is the most likely.

⁹ (Surat al-Buruj

-One of the formal features of this copy is also the use of shaping in it and We did not find this in the copy of the Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies.

-As well as the formal features that we note the occurrence of some corrections to some words in the margin , and the transcriber corrected some of the words written in the text in the way of writing off , and a second case of skepticism in reading and writing the correct ones above the word or on the margin, for example:

-Corrections Some words in the margin, as stated on page No. (9) of the manuscript, and made a correction to the author's name in the margin ,(figure 8)

-page (10) line (7)

- On page (33) of the manuscript, line (16), the word on the margin in the north side was corrected.

- On page (46), line (9), the word in the margin was corrected.

- On page (48), line (18), the word in the margin was corrected

The transcriber also used deletion in correcting some words, for example the correction by deletion on page No. (55)line (17) and he marked a deletion mark for the text and added the correct one in the margin .(figure 10)

- On page (66) in line (8), we find that the copier was written off on the word without making a correction to it in the margin.(figure 11)

-Graduations that appeared on this copy: -

These represent the graduations or appendices written by the author In the margin and they were written by the hand of Al-Biruni to explain or Explanation more to the paragraphs that need interpretation, and we

find that the transcriber of this copy did not integrate the graduations into the text as some of the transcribers do, but left it as it is , while the previous version of Al-Biruni that was at Institute and preserved at the Silk Road University, we find that the transcriber integrated the graduations into the text of the manuscript , and if we follow the graduations that appeared on this manuscript, we find that it amounts to fourteen graduations, and we will show some of them to know the formal dimension of the manuscript .

Graduation No. (1) is located on page (4) in the left margin from the bottom, and we note that the font used in writing is slightly slanted, and we find that Al-Biruni followed the recognized methodology to which the sources referred in how to write statements or comments in the margins , and this graduation came in three parallel horizontal lines. We also note that there is another graduation on the right side of the bottom of the page written in a slightly italicized font. (figure12)

Graduation (2) is located on page (11) of the manuscript, line (3), where the graduation came on the left side of the writing, which is an explanation of the text in this pag

- Graduation No. (3) on page No. (27), line (1) of the page, and the graduation came in the Nastaqi font at the top of the page. (figure 13)

- Graduation No. (4) on page No. (42), line (6). The graduation is written in italics upwards and consists of two paragraphs below each other.

-Graduation No. (5) Page No. (51) Line (1) came at the top of the page in the margin consisting of six lines.

- Graduation (6) came on page (145) in line (16) and it came in two lines in black color.

- Graduation No. (7) on page No. (145) in line (16) and came up with four lines from the right side of the text in the margin space.

- Graduation (8) came on page (150) in line (17) on the left side of the text and was written in black.

- Graduation (9) came on page (185) in line (4) on the left side is three horizontal lines.

- Graduation (10) came on page (183) in line (9) is two lines.

- The Graduation (11) came on page (187) in line (6) and came horizontally, consisting of seven lines in black color in the margin to the right of the text.

- Graduation (12) came on page (213), line (9), consisting of two lines.

- Graduation (13) came on page (218), line (14) to the left of the text in three lines,

- Graduation (14), page (224), the first line at the top of the page in the Nasta'iq font, consisting of five lines.

- We find that Graduations are followed by an archaeological dimension in the study of the manuscript, including:

- Highlighting the extent of adoption of the corrected version with graduations in the copies that were later copied.

- The position of the transcriber on the integration of some of the graduations in the version reviewed by Al-Biruni as an important indicator of the investigations of this version.

- The importance of late copies as archaeological copies in embodying the culture of its times associated with the copying of manuscripts and the methodologies of those copies.

CONCLUSION

After the study of the copy preserved at Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies and preserved in the Silk Road university, the results of the study can be drawn as follows:

- We find that the transcriber and the author followed the methodology followed in copying the manuscripts, and correcting the errors in the margin, which indicates the awareness of the transcriber and the author of these rules.

-We find that a correction was made to some words in both copies, whether the copy preserved at Al-Biruni Institute for Oriental Studies and preserved in the Silk Road university, as well as for the copy kept in Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library.

-In the framework of the formal review and tracking of both copies that have been studied in this research, we note the effort of the scribe and the author in directing both copies of the study, which represents two stages, the stage that precedes the review of the manuscript by the author, and the stage that comes after the review of the manuscript by the author.

-Introducing the author and the manuscript to understand more about the two versions of the study.

- The difference of the first page of each of the two versions of the study, and this is due to the fact that this brocade

was added by transcriber for both copies, which confirms that both copies belong to the same author, but were copied by different copyist, and the difference of the text helped us to identify the culture of each of the copyist of these two copies.

-After tracing the copy kept in Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library, and comparing it to the Persian copy, we find that it was incomplete, missing from it 30 pages.

- The study proved that there had been a change in the title of the manuscript, as it was mentioned in the manuscript preserved at the Silk Roads University under the name, Kitab Al Tafhim Li Awail Sinaat AL- Tanjim " but in the copy of manuscript Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library it was called "at-Tafhīm fī 'ilm at-tanġīm"

(1) A copy of the manuscript of Kitab Al Tafhīm Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjīm in the Silk Road International University.

(2) A map of the world from a manuscript of Kitab Al Tafhīm Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjīm to Al-Biruni in the Silk Road International University.

(3) A map of the world from a manuscript of Kitab Al Tafhīm Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjīm to Al-Biruni Quoting, Translated by Ramzy Zein ,

(4) First page of the manuscript of Kitab Al Tafhim Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjim, in-Biruni Institute of Oriental Studies, Tashkent.

(5)The second page is the preserved manuscript of Kitab Al Tafhim Li Awail Sinaat AL-Tanjim to Al-Biruni , Al-Biruni Institute of Oriental Studies, Tashkent

(6) First page of the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fī ‘ilm at-tanġīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

(7) Second pag of the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fi ‘ilm at-tanġīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

(8) corrected some of the words in the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fi ‘ilm at-tanġīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

(9) corrected some of the words in the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fi ‘ilm at-tanġīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

(10) deletion and correcting some of the words in the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fi ‘ilm at-tanġīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

(11) deletion and correcting some of the words in the manuscript “at-Tafhīm fi ‘ilm at-tangīm” to Biruni in the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin library

12. Graduation No. (1)

13. Graduation No. (3)